

Bamaa: A STEM Learning Platform for Afghan Students

Abstract—Decades of conflict and poverty have devastated Afghanistan’s education system, leaving curricula outdated, poor quality education and shorten human resources. Although Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) learning platforms have seen widespread global adoption, Afghan learners remain largely excluded due to language barriers, limited awareness, low digital literacy, lack of trust, financial constraint and the situation worsened by the nationwide education ban on girls and women.

To address this gap, we introduce Bamaa, a platform to support students in Afghanistan in improving their problem-solving skills in STEM subjects. The platform support Dari and Pashto (Afghanistan’s native languages), enabling an inclusive personalized learning and individual feedback and recommendation learning experience for students navigating educational barriers caused by years of political instability, poverty and the restrictive policies imposed by the current regime on women.

Index Terms—Generative AI, Afghanistan, Education, STEM

I. INTRODUCTION

The global rise of GenAI such as ChatGPT, Gemini, and others has revolutionized human-machine interaction and improved access to knowledge [1], their usefulness remains limited in the Afghan communities. On the other hand, Digital literacy remains a challenge as many students lack the technical skills to effectively use these advanced and multi-functional platforms. The current generative AI tools are designed for general global audiences and can overwhelm students unfamiliar with modern digital environments. Therefore, a simplified AI educational platform that is tailored specifically to Afghanistan’s students’ needs, curriculum, and languages is essential.

For girls, the barriers are even higher. It has been four years since women and girls were banned from attending school beyond the sixth grade [2], cutting off their path to education and future careers. Bamaa platform can help bridge the gap simply by tracking progress, offering step-by-step guidance, and allowing each learner to practice and get clear explanations whenever they are stuck.

Poverty is another major reason that the families prioritize their survival on the education of their kids [3] to reduce the household or another very common solution is to involve their kid in labor.

II. CHALLENGES

Afghan students are facing a multitude of educational challenges, ranging from outdated or inconsistent curricula to the complete lack of access to supplementary education materials in public schools. Moreover, it has been difficult

to find quality teachers and instructors not only in big cities but also in rural areas. According to a study only 36% of schools possess the minimum classroom resources required for effective learning, including a functional blackboard, exercise books, and basic writing tools such as pens or pencils [4]. Consequently, Students who wish to strengthen their academic skills particularly in STEM subjects often turn to private centers. However, these centers are costly and only operate in big cities. The rural students make up a significant share of total student population in the country. These students potentially face multiple challenges including, travel cost, accommodation cost, food cost, and psychological stress, among many. Bamaa would be instantly accessible through multiple devices, including computers, tablets, and mobile phones, at much lower cost and location constraints but with access to high quality learning materials.

While these barriers affect all students, the situation is especially dire for girls and women who are currently denied formal schooling beyond class 6 or elementary school [5]. Bamaa will provide safe access, quality learning materials and personalized learning journey by a virtual learning environment that keeps track of student’s progress. Bamaa is designed to fill the gap created by the lack of schools, teachers, and mentors, by providing students with high-quality learning materials and proactive guidance throughout their educational journey leveraging the GenAI.

Low Digital literacy awareness and educational system adaptation challenges with Generative AI are crucial components to success in Afghanistan. Bamaa addresses the biggest challenge in adopting Generative AI in education—complexity and system readiness—by streamlining AI for students and educators. At the same time, it leverages Gen AI to enhance the entire educational system, making learning more efficient, personalized, and effective.

A recent survey [6] found that students consider studying through mobile devices, computers, and tablets both effective and satisfying. These results highlight that technology-based e-learning offers a flexible and accessible solution for students across Afghanistan, regardless of location. This reinforces the importance of platforms like Bamaa, which delivers educational content across multiple devices while optimizing for low-bandwidth and limited internet environments, ensuring students can access quality learning materials even where connectivity is slow or costly.

III. ADVANTAGES OF THE APPLICATION

The strength of Bamaa is listed below.

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- Bilingual support: Another key strength of Bamaa is its bilingual support. Bamaa’s interface and explanations are provided in Dari and Pashto, enabling students with limited Dari proficiency to comfortably use the app.
- Resource accessibility, cost and time efficiency: This platform also addresses critical issues of accessibility, cost, and time efficiency. The rural students do not have to travel to cities to access tuition centers and printed sources. Bamaa enables students to access high-quality content directly from their personal devices with minimum cost.
- Personalization: In Bamaa, the math problems are categorized into three levels: easy, moderate, and advanced and the continuous assessment of the students’ performance will adjust the difficulty of suggested problems. It also provides feedback on the areas of improvement.
- Continuous Assessment: The dashboard allows students to track their activity and improvements over time
- Suitability in Afghanistan: Considering the limited internet bandwidth in rural area and partially in big cities, Bamaa is offering the main features optimized to work on low connectivity environments.
- Women empowerment: the platform remains a safe place for Afghan women to progressively improve their skill critical and problem-solving skills. Bamaa will assist them to continue learning independently from their homes and keep themselves connected to academic development and future opportunities.
- Unlike other GenAI platforms, Bamaa is focused and designed for students’ unique needs. It leverages the generative AI models to ensure accurate problem solving and clear explanations.
- Community-based feature: It enables learners to provide feedback on the accuracy of answers and suggest areas for enhancement.

IV. BAMA A DEVELOPMENT STAGE:

The prototype phase of the Bamaa platform has been successfully completed, and the system is currently undergoing internal testing to ensure readiness for user engagement. At its core, the platform leverages the GenAI model designed to process and convert Dari-language text content from images into a structured, readable format. A key focus of this process is the model’s ability to accurately extract Dari text and embedded mathematical notation or formulas within questions. The platform’s core functionality includes extracting text from images, interpreting question content, and selecting the correct option from multiple-choices. We also do human validation for AI generation, which ensures correctness of AI extraction, and its agentic workflow.

V. PARTNERSHIPS AND COLLABORATION

Bamaa is open to partnerships with schools, educational institutions, and international organizations. At present, our primary cooperating targets are schools in Afghanistan and international/local organizations which work on educating girls

and high school students. Currently, we are actively seeking international partnerships, particularly with organizations that can provide funding support and credible certification opportunities for Afghan students who are unable to pursue formal studies. In this way, Bamaa aims to become a bridge between international organizations and underserved students inside Afghanistan. This platform is being developed by dedicated, passionate, skilled, set of afghan who loves to bring sustainable changes in education. While substantial progress has already been achieved including AI extraction proof of concept (POC), Agentic workflow POC, development of student dashboard, Database design and development, and human validation workflow. We are actively seeking funding opportunities to support the next stages of development like completion of the frontend, cover cloud resource expenses (such as token consumption costs and infrastructure), platform scalability, security, and maintenance. Moreover, future iterations of the platform will incorporate a feedback mechanism based on user interactions which will require additional infrastructure and resources.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

Education in Afghanistan is marked by deep inequalities in access, resources, and outcomes. Platforms like Bamaa would play a crucial role in overcoming these challenges. Bamaa provides a variety of questions and answers all together for the learners in different levels to practice and improve their problem-solving skills. Key concerns such as cost efficiency, readability, and content credibility have been carefully addressed in the platform’s design. Currently, Bamaa operates in both Dari and Pashto, with plans to add English in the future to help students become more familiar with international academic environments and better prepare for global learning opportunities.

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